

An Evaluation of Time Series Foundation Models' on Short Horizon Forecasting With Limited Data

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Abstract. The Monash time series forecasting competition is increasingly showing the power of machine learning to accurately perform time series forecasting. However, a notable limitation of these methods is that they require large amounts of data for training. This can make machine learning methods prohibitive to deploy in practice. A proposed solution is to pre-train foundation models on very large corpora of time series data and generalise the learning to more specific tasks. While numerous time series foundation models have been presented, very few of these have been assessed on short horizon time series forecasting. 4 methods that utilise time series foundation models were compared to state of the art forecasting methods. The results indicate some improved accuracy in forecasting longer time series with few training examples, however, the methods struggled with shorter series compared to conventional methods.

Keywords: Forecasting, Short Horizon Time Series, Foundation Model.

1 Introduction

Time series forecasting is an important challenge in healthcare. By analysing historical data such as hospital admissions, medication usage, or vital signs, hospitals can efficiently allocate resources and enhance early intervention strategies. However, a common challenge in healthcare is a lack of historic data, particularly individual patient data, which can greatly limit the effectiveness of time series forecasting in practice.

Results from the Monash time series forecasting competitions have highlighted that pure machine learning (ML) methods have become the state of the art (SOTA) in forecasting [1]. However, a common limitation of these methods is that they require many sample time series and long sequences to learn from. This makes the use of many ML methods prohibitive when working with patient data. However, a recent class of methods proposes a solution to this limitation; time series foundation (TSF) models.

TSF models are large-scale, pre-trained neural networks designed to understand and predict patterns across diverse time series data from multiple domains. These models aim to create a universal system capable of handling various time series tasks without requiring dataset-specific training. It has been proposed that these methods can greatly benefit settings where data is lacking, as is often the case in healthcare.

This study reviews 4 recent methods that utilise TSF models: TimeLLM [2], Chronos [3], UniTS [4] and TimeMoE [5].

Time-LLM presents a reprogramming framework to repurpose Large Language Models (LLMs) for general time series forecasting with the backbone language model kept intact. TimeLLM reprograms an embedding-visible LLM (such as LLaMA or GPT-2). Rather than fine-tuning the LLM, TimeLLM teaches the model to take time series input and output forecasts while keeping the LLM frozen. The approach uses a "Prompt-as-Prefix" technique to align time series modality with natural language prompt text, enabling the LLM to reason about temporal patterns.

Chronos is a framework to minimally adapt LLMs for time series forecasting. It uses simple scaling and quantisation to convert continuous time series values into discrete tokens. These are interpreted by a pre-trained family of zero-shot forecasters using the T5 architecture [6].

UniTS (Unified Time Series model) utilises a large foundation model pre-trained on a very large corpora of time-series data to process generative and predictive tasks with shared parameters. UniTS employs a modified transformer block to capture universal time series representations, enabling transferability from its pre-training dataset of diverse domains and traits. The model uses patch tokenisation to integrate the diverse learned patterns from its extensive training to a wide range of time series tasks.

Finally, Time-MoE (Time-Mixture of Experts) comprises a family of decoder-only time series foundation models, designed to operate in an auto-regressive manner. Time-MoE leverages a sparse mixture-of-experts design, to efficiently activate specialist pre-trained networks that are specialists in particular data traits to more effectively generate expert forecasts.

While all methods utilise a TSF model backbone, Time-LLM is unique in this set, as the only method to reprogram existing LLMs rather than training a new model. Time-MoE stands out with its mixture-of-experts architecture that provides efficiency through sparse activation. UniTS is distinguished by its multi-task capability, handling forecasting, classification, imputation, and anomaly detection in a single model. Chronos focuses specifically on minimal adaptation of existing language models (T5) through simple quantisation techniques and emphasises probabilistic forecasting with data augmentation strategies. While Time-LLM and Chronos leverage existing LLM architectures, Time-MoE and UniTS develop specialised time series transformer architectures optimised for temporal data.

1.1 Contribution

Of the methods reviewed in this survey, only TimeLLM has previously reported results for short horizon forecasting. This survey seeks to validate their results and compare a range of TSF models' performance on short timeseries. The TSF methods will be compared against a set of SOTA forecasting benchmarks, chosen for their previously reported success in generating accurate short horizon forecasts. This will demonstrate the potential for TSF to be used to generate accurate forecasts in settings like healthcare.

2 Method

2.1 Foundation Model Selection

The reviewed TSM models were selected on basis of ease of implementation, and do not represent a comprehensive review of all available TSF models. However, they do represent the range of architectures used in TSF models described in Miller et al. [7].

2.2 Baseline Model Selection

Baseline models were selected to represent a range of SOTA forecasting techniques, representing statistical, ML and hybrid methods. Table 1 provides a summary of the baseline methods selected.

Table 1. Summary of baseline methods used to benchmark foundation models against.

Method	Type	Architecture
PatchTST	Pure machine learning	Multi-head self-attention applied to time series patches and encoder layers with attention blocks and feed-forward networks.
NHITS	Pure machine learning	Stack of neural blocks with pooling/interpolation layers, each block containing fully connected layers that operate at different temporal resolutions.
Dlinear	Hybrid	Uses moving average decomposition to separate trend and seasonal components, then applies separate linear neural network layers to each component.
ARIMA	Statistical	Based on mathematical modeling of time series components estimated using maximum likelihood estimation.

2.3 Data Selection, Implementation and Evaluation

This experiment followed the guidelines of the M4 Forecasting Competition [8]. The M4 dataset consists of 100,000 time series, representing hourly, daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly and yearly frequencies. The data was reproduced from real world samples from a wide range of domains. Table 2 provides a summary of the data and the forecasting horizons for each set. This data was chosen for this experiment, as it is openly available, is commonly used for benchmarking and contains time series that are much shorter than those typically presented when authors evaluate new methods.

Each experiment was initially run with the default hyperparameters for each method, with key hyperparameters being optimised using a basic gridsearch method. As each method had different adjustable hyperparameters, no consistent pattern of adjustment was able to be applied to each method. All experiments were run using a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 GPU with 12GB of memory.

As the scale varied between each time series the metric used to evaluate the accuracy of each method’s forecasts was the mean Symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage Error (sMAPE). sMAPE measures the average percentage error between predicted and actual values, providing a scale independent measurement of forecasting error.

Table 2. Summary of M4 data used in this experiment.

Frequency	Number of series	Mean series length	Forecasting horizon
Hourly	414	902	48
Daily	4227	2371	14
Weekly	359	1035	13
Monthly	48000	234	18
Quarterly	24000	100	8
Yearly	23000	37	6

3 Results

Table 3 shows the average sMAPE for each task. Lower scores equate to greater accuracy. The most accurate method is highlighted in red and the second in blue.

Table 3. Summary of experimental results. The mean sMAPE achieved by each method for all series is recorded in line with the dataset frequency on the left.

	TSF models				Baseline models			
	Chronos	TimeLLM	TimeMoE	UniTS	PatchTST	NHITS	DLinear	ARIMA
Hourly	7.698	35.974	10.991	33.355	20.056	15.075	19.767	36.798
Daily	2.922	4.437	3.601	27.202	3.318	2.993	3.781	3.365
Weekly	5.926	11.84	7.953	46.503	9.265	8.697	9.872	8.884
Monthly	13.663	28.277	14.949	23.421	15.683	13.524	19.638	13.989
Quarterly	10.761	15.207	13.442		16.658	10.565	15.178	10.297
Yearly	16.301	23.718	21.821	27.495	16.151	14.888	27.974	16.226

Notably, TimeLLM and UniTS struggled with all datasets presented in this task. It is possible that UniTS may have been hampered by being trained for a wide range of time series tasks. With the limited data presented in M4 the UniTS model may have struggled to adapt to this task. Additionally, UniTS utilises patch tokenisation, which combines multiple time points into a tokenised patch. With the shorter time series in the M4 data, this may have hampered the performance of this method.

Likewise, TimeLLM may have performed poorly because of the lengthy text prompt to initiate forecasts not being suitable to capture the local patterns necessary for short horizon forecasting. It should be noted that, TimeLLM is the only method to report forecasting results for the M4 data in their original paper [2], where their sMAPE error was much lower (Yearly- 13.4, Quarterly- 10.1, Monthly- 13.0, others- 4.8). However, this study was not able to replicate this.

However, TimeMoE and Chronos performed strongly across all datasets. In particular, these methods outperformed the baselines in the majority of cases where there were few timeseries to learn from (hourly, daily and weekly data), highlighting the ability of these models to quickly adapt and produce accurate forecasts without having

to perform dataset specific training. On the other hand, it should be noted that the traditional baseline methods still outperformed the TSF methods in the data where the time series were shortest and there was a lot of example series to learn from.

4 Conclusion

This survey has highlighted that a potential strength of TSF methods is their ability to be deployed in settings without many training examples and outperform the current SOTA. However, it also highlights that the surveyed methods continue to underperform when time series are short in length. But, this work has only surveyed a sample of TSF methods and others may perform better in this setting.

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